

SECOND VICTIM PHENOMENON THE PERIOPERATIVE PROVIDERS PERSPECTIVE

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Background

Adverse events have the potential to cause harm to the patient and the healthcare professional.

- One in three healthcare professionals will be exposed to an adverse event.
- Many healthcare organizations lack an organized form of support for the healthcare professional.
- 68% of the time healthcare professionals do not receive support from the healthcare organization

Evidence suggests that organized supportive interventions optimize the wellbeing for the healthcare professional.

Purpose

The purpose of the project is to develop a set of recommendations through which perioperative team members can receive support following adverse events.

Aims

- Aim A: Assess current resources available to the perioperative team at the time of an adverse event.
- Aim B: Assess perioperative teams' experience with adverse event.
- Aim C: Provide the project facility recommendations based on the perioperative team needs for support after adverse events.

Methods

- Design: Quality Improvement Focus groups SOAR analysis, Prospective cross-sectional
- Setting: Perioperative at a tertiary medical center in Southern California
- Participants: SOAR analysis Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetist (n=50), Second Victim Experience Support Tool Nurses (n=14), Surgical technicians (n=4)
- Measures: Second Victim Experience Support Tool Survey (29 questions 5-point Likert scale)

Adapted Iowa Model: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Health

Results

SOAR Analysis	
Strengths	Opportunities

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer support strong in some facilities • Union peer support program • Employee Assistance Program | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with the Support 4 You Second Victim Program so it can be available for Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) • Develop a policy to ensure all CRNAs are offered the same interventions |
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Aspirations	Results
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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the well-being of CRNAs • Supportive interventions that need to take place post-event • A break after the event and ability to step out • Re assignment when errors occur | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 2021, review preoperative policies related to Adverse events with a focus on the resources for the second victims • By 2022 develop a policy on the process and procedures following an adverse event with a focus second victim care • In 2022, collaborate with the hospital administration and human resources to create a peer support program |
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Second Victim Experience and Support Tool Psychological & Physical Health

Second Victim Experience and Support Tool Forms of Support

Second Victim Experience and Support Tool Professional Outcomes

Discussion

- Findings are congruent with literature.
- The perioperative provider desires peer support following an adverse event
- It is the goal of this project to make recommendations to leadership based on the perioperative providers needs following adverse events.

Desired Forms of Support

Future Implications

- Healthcare organization will benefit from assessing the needs of healthcare professionals following adverse events.
- A systematic approach focused on the needs of the healthcare professional will provide valuable information on the support needed to improve the wellbeing of the healthcare professional.

Selected References

